

ENHANCEMENT ON AUTOMATED PREFORMING FOR COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

The Advanced Ply Placement is a novel technology for automated fiber layup, based on unidirectional fabrics. Recent research activities have been working on the placement of dry reinforcement fabrics. Due to the absence of tack, auxiliary binder systems are necessary for layer adhesion. These auxiliaries can be divided into reactive and non-reactive binder systems and vary in terms of appearance, chemical composition, processing conditions and tack. This paper presents the results of investigations into solubility of different binder systems in epoxy resins and their effects on thermo-mechanical properties. It is shown, that reactive binder systems offer superior solubility under different processing conditions, when compared to non-reactive binder systems. Furthermore, it is presented that non-reactive binder system decrease the glass temperature of epoxy resins by up to 10°C. The results give an overview of the usability of binder materials during manual and automated preforming processes.

1 INTRODUCTION

The European Union's Clean Sky 2 (CS2) joint research programme has been launched in 2015 with the aim to further pursue the achievements of Clean Sky 1. With an overall budget of 4 BN € more than 600 participating entities from 24 countries will push the European competitiveness in cutting edge technologies and environmental friendly production methods on a new level. Clean Sky 2 is covering all major topics off innovative aviation research to answer the question how affordable and eco-friendly aviation will look like in the 21st century.

The Institute of Aircraft Design (IFB) at the University of Stuttgart is involved in the CS2 sub-branch "AIRFRAME ITD" and is responsible for research on the field of new and efficient manufacturing technologies for composite materials. The main goals are to decrease production costs at increased process efficiency as well as to lower the ecological impact of the entire composite production chain. The paper will present the actual status of the Advanced Ply Placement (APP), which has been developed at IFB for the automated layup of unidirectional prepreg tapes. Within ecoTECH the process will be enhanced, so that dry reinforcement fabrics can be placed directly onto double curved surfaces.

1.1 ADVANCED PLY PLACEMENT

The Automated Tape Laying (ATL) process is an established technology for the automated production of fiber reinforced structures in the aerospace industry. Unidirectional tapes, with a width of up to 300 mm, can be placed onto structures with low complexity, such as wing skins. When placing wide unidirectional fabrics onto double-curved surfaces, differences in length between the inner and outer fabric edges appear. ATL systems carry the reinforcement material on reels, which are mounted at the placement head. A compensation of these length differences during the layup process can therefore not be realized without causing wrinkles. Due to the high weight of the layup head (incl. material storage) most ATL systems are installed on gantry systems [1].

Szceny et al. [2] has introduced a technology for the automated manufacturing of complex, large-scaled carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) structures in the transport sector. With the Advanced Ply

Placement (APP) the wrinkle-free placement of unidirectional, pre-impregnated fabrics onto double-curved surfaces can be realized [3]. The APP was developed for cost-efficient and flexible composite manufacturing of snap-cure Out of Autoclave (OoA) prepreg materials to avoid cost-intensive and complex curing in autoclaves [4]. Three cooperating robots imitate the manual placement of fiber mats, as it can be seen in Figure 1. Two industrial robots (ABB 6700 MH3), that are equipped with pneumatic grippers, transport the pre-cut fabrics from a material supply station over the tooling mould (see Figure 1). To extend the range of the two six-axis robots, they are mounted on linear axes. A third robot (ABB 6650S) has a compaction roller attached to the sixth axis, which drapes the fabric into the mould (Figure 2). Therefore, the compaction roller presses the fabric against the mould surface and moves in direction of the reinforcement fibers to one of the grippers. The gripper robots adjust their position according to pre-defined trajectories, so that tension is applied at all times to avoid wrinkling of the fabric. As soon as the compaction roller has reached its end position next to the first gripper unit, it moves back to the initial starting point and repeats this process towards the second gripper unit. Plies are placed next to each other without gaps or overlaps and the whole layup procedure is repeated until the entire layer is finalized. The tooling mould is mounted on a rotary axis, so that all different fiber orientations can be realized. A ply book describes the layup of the composite structure, in which the different fiber orientations and the stacking sequence is considered to meet the mechanical requirements. According to this ply book, the orientation of the mould is set and subsequent plies can be placed.

Figure 1: a) APP Process Scheme b) APP Prepreg Layup

The fabrics are manually pre-cut on a separate material supply station. The absence of a cutting mechanism on the APP layup head reduces its complexity to a minimum. Additionally, the external material storage and supply enables the usage of flexible six-axis industrial robots. In comparison to rolled fabrics, pre-cut fabrics show better manipulability. The single plies are clamped in single 20 mm wide gripper elements that can be moved relatively to each other. To compensate length-differences during the layup process axial shearing of the unidirectional plies is used (Figure 2). At any time during the layup process, a defined and constant tape tension can be ensured due to pneumatic control of the single gripper elements.

Figure 2: APP; (a) Shape-Adaptive Compaction Roller (b) Ply Shearing

The second key component for the wrinkle free ply layup is the shape adaptive compaction roller (Figure 2). In state-of-the-art (SoA) manufacturing technologies, such as the Automated Fiber Placement (AFP) or ATL, cast silicone rollers are used to achieve the required compaction pressure during the deposition process and to compensate for minimal curvatures in the tool. A constant pressure over the entire tape width cannot be guaranteed. Comparable to the segmented grippers, the pressure roller of the APP process was divided into single segments. A flexible silicone membrane is tensioned over several pneumatic tandem cylinders. This approach enables the compaction roller to adapt to double-curved surfaces and a defined pressure across the entire tape width can be set.

Besides the layup of pre-impregnated fabrics, dry fiber placement (DFP) is investigated as well. Due to current use of prepreg fabrics and their extensive tack at room temperature, plies can be placed and fixed onto the tool surface or previously placed plies. The use of dry fabrics and lacking tackiness, however, requires the use of auxiliary binder materials and activating methods [5]. The main benefit of utilizing dry fibers is that subsequently less energy is needed for cost-intensive, refrigerated prepreg storage. Furthermore, material costs can be reduced and complex curing cycles in the autoclave can be replaced. Only a few prepreg resins are currently available, which limits the use for many applications. In SoA liquid resin infusion (LRI) processes, a variety of commercially available reactive resins can be used and customer-specific needs and requirements can be met. The development of DFP within the Advanced Ply Placement robotic cell represents an extension of the processing window.

1.2 BINDER MATERIALS

Due to lack of tack for dry fabrics, additional auxiliaries, so-called binder or tackifying agents are necessary to fix the tapes to the mold surface or previous plies. These binder systems can be divided into thermoplastic (non-reactive) and thermosetting (reactive) systems [6]. The majority of tackifying agents possesses no tack at room temperature and has to be heated up until their specific melting or application temperature. With the application of additional pressure, two joining partners (fabrics with binder applied) are consolidated and due to cooling and crystallization (non-reactive binders) or curing (reactive binder), they are fixed together. Binder systems are commercially available in different shapes and styles. They can be distinguished in powder binders, textile binder (veils, webs and yarns) as well as spray-on or hot-melt binder systems. During handling, the appearance of the binder has no significant role. Only the binder application and the adjustment of a specific binder areal weight can be affected and it is more challenging with powder binders and spray applications. Several methods for binder activation can be applied [5] [7]. During automated manufacturing processes, the application of radiation energy is most common. In most processes, infrared-heaters or diode-lasers are installed [1]. The heat output can thereby be focused and selective and local binder activation can be realized. It is well known that binder systems affect mechanical properties. Brody and Gillespie [8] state that the use of reactive binder systems result in higher peel strengths of preforms. Non-reactive tackifying agents (thermoplastics) reduce mechanical properties [9] in terms of E-Modulus, mechanical strength, etc. On the other hand, Arnold et al. [10] state that the use of a thermoplastic binder can improve the fracture toughness of composite materials. Impact resistance and the susceptibility to delamination is one major concern that composites have to deal with. In many cases, a compromise between required mechanical properties and impact resistance has to be found. The reason for reduced mechanical properties of composites structures with integrated thermoplastic binders is the fact that thermoplastic adhesives are not soluble in thermosetting epoxy resins and they do not interact in the cross-linking of the resin system. Therefore, non-reactive binders will remain as foreign objects in the neat resin or composite part, with local inhomogeneous mechanical properties. Tackifying agent may also reduce the preform permeability [11] and soluble binders can increase resin viscosity and prevent filling of the mold [12].

The ongoing research covers a screening of several state-of-the-art binder systems for dry fiber preforming. Different sample types, e.g. neat binder samples and binder-resin mixtures have been considered during testing. The implementation of binder particles into the matrix during the curing process was investigated by the use of micrographs and influencing effects on the glass transition temperature has been investigated using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC).

2 EXPERIMENTATION METHODOLOGY

Seven different binder systems (Table 1) have been analysed in the course of this study. These different tackifying agents can be divided into reactive and non-reactive binder systems and vary in terms of appearance, chemical composition, processing conditions and tack.

Table 1: Binder Systems

Name	Abbreviation	Supplier	Bindertype	Chemical Composition	Appearance	Activation Temperature [°C]
EPIKOTE 05311	E5311	HEXION	Reactive	Bisphenol A	Powder	97 - 107
EPIKOTE 05390	E5390	HEXION	Reactive	Bisphenol A	Powder	75 - 105
Araldite LT3366	LT3366	HUNTSMAN	Reactive	Bisphenol A	Powder	160 - 200
SAERfix EP	SAER	SAERTEX	Reactive	N.A.	Veil	RT
MGS PR685	PR685	HEXION	Reactive	Bisphenol A	Hot-Melt	RT
PA1541	PA1541	Spunfab	Non-Reactive	CoPolyamide	Veil	87 - 100
AIRTAC 2E	AIR2E	AIRTECH	Non-Reactive	Rubber-Based	Spray	RT

The binder systems EPIKOTE 05311, EPIKOTE 05390 and HUNTSMAN Araldite LT 3366 are reactive binders, based on Bisphenol A. They are available as white powders with different grain sizes (E5311: 90 - 125 μm ; E5390: 50 - 90 μm ; LT3366: 160 - 200 μm) [13]. The activation temperatures vary between 75 - 200 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, according to Table 1. Due to their appearance as powder, the application during on site preforming processes automated binder application modules are necessary to achieve stable and accurate binder areal weights.

The SAERfix EP from SAERTEX is a self-adhesive veil, which is compatible with epoxy resins due to its chemical cross-linking with the matrix system in the course of curing. The technical data sheet (TDS) states, that SAERfix EP has no negative influence on the mechanical characteristics of composite materials. Due to its tack at room temperature, binder activation is not necessary and the veil, which is available in different areal weights, can directly be adhered onto the reinforcement fabric and subsequently be processed.

HEXION EPIKOTE Resin MGS PR685 is a high-viscous resin component, based on Bisphenol A. Because of its high viscosity at room temperature ($>> 30\,000\text{ mPas}$), the binder has to be heated up in a pneumatic hot-melt glue gun (BÜHNEN HB700 K spray) and is applied at elevated temperatures above 100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (2000-3200 mPas). In the experiments, the application temperature was set to 120 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The TDS states that the PR685 completely dissolves in Hexion's Liquid Resin Infusion (LRI) matrix systems. When compared to other tackifying agents, it does not represent any voids or foreign matter in fibre reinforced plastic parts and an impact of PR685 on mechanical properties is not apparent.

Spunfab PA1541 is a Copolyamid with a melting temperature between 87 - 100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. PA 1541 is commercially available as a thermoplastic veil with different areal weights, starting at 3 g/m^2 . Most commonly, the pre-measured non-reactive veils are applied via a heated calender during fabric production. The veil has no tack at room temperature and therefore has no effect on storage or handling. Pre-measured veils make it easy to control and adjust the binder fraction.

AIRTAC 2E is a rubber-based spray adhesive for temporary fixation on vertical or complex surfaces. AIRTAC 2E is commercially available in aerosol cans and is tacky at room temperature after the solvents have evaporated. However, the appropriate use of AIRTAC 2E needs to be discussed and thoroughly analyzed since the binder is based on rubber, which most likely will remain in the composite material as foreign matter and affect the mechanical and thermo-mechanical properties.

2.1 BINDER SOLUBILITY

In this study, the solubility of different tackifying agents in epoxy resins shall be analyzed, since reactive and non-reactive binder materials are expected to behave differently when added to a liquid neat resin sample. Therefore, three different epoxy resins are the basis for the solubility tests: SIKA Biresin CR120 / CH120-6, HEXION EPIKOTE MGS RIM 135 / EPIKURE MGS RIMH 1366 and RESOLTECH 1500 / 1504. All systems are epoxy-based resins with a low viscosity for LRI

processes, such as Vacuum Assisted Resin Infusion (VARI) or Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM). The mixing ratio was taken from the manufacturers TDS and is set to 100:30±2 parts by weight (Resin : Hardener). Samples of 10 g (7.7 g resin and 2.3 g hardener) are prepared for the test specimen. Different binder systems are added to the mixed epoxy resin samples. The grammatures correspond to a binder fraction of 5 wt% relative to the fiber areal weight of the fabric, which is an industry approved amount of binder to achieve sufficient tack during processing. With a presumed fiber areal weight of 100 gsm and a fiber volume fraction of 60%, the binder fraction results in 1 g. The binder was added and manually stirred for 3 minutes at room temperature. A pipette is used for extraction of a resin drop, which is applied onto a slide for subsequent microscope analysis. The aforementioned procedure is not applicable for all binder types. The binder veil Spunfab PA 1541 was precut and applied onto the slide. A drop of neat resin was subsequently put onto the veil. AIRTAC 2E is supplied in an aerosol can and needs to be sprayed into the mixing bucket beforehand. The epoxy sample is poured in afterwards. The samples are degassed for 5 minutes at 50 mbar absolute pressure and subsequent curing of binder / epoxy resin samples at elevated temperatures was carried out in a convection oven. Different samples are cured at varying temperatures. The curing temperature is increased from room temperature to 120°C in 20°C increments. After curing of the different binder / epoxy samples, the slides were investigated with a SoA light microscope (Leitz Metallux 3). The samples were analyzed for any remaining foreign objects and binder residue in the epoxy resin.

2.2 EFFECTS ON THERMO-MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

In this study the effects of different tackifying agents on thermo-mechanical properties of the Resoltech 1500/1504 resin is analysed via Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC). With the help of calorimetry, the heat quantity is analysed, that is necessary for physical or chemical transformation of a material [14]. The result of a DSC analysis is a curve of heat flux versus temperature. DSC can be used to analyse the glass transition of polymers. When the glass transition temperature (T_g) is exceeded, the mobility of chain segments is increased and polymers soften. The temperature range, in which the transition occurs, is called glass transition area and starts at the Onset Point (T_{Onset}). The T_g and T_{Onset} are dependent from the chemical structure as well as the degree of cross-linking.

The epoxy resin Resoltech 1500 / 1504 is set as test basis for DSC analysis. According to chapter 2.1 different binder materials with a binder fraction of 5 wt% have been added and the single specimen have been cured in a convection oven (Mettmert UF260 Plus) with the cure cycle given by the manufacturer (3h at 50°C; 3h at 100°C and 3h at 150°C). Six DSC samples for every single binder resin mixture and the neat resin have been prepared with a sample weight of 12 mgs. Differential Scanning Calorimetry analysis has been carried out with the DSC2920 from TA Instruments. To delete the thermal background, two single DSC cycles from room temperature to 180°C at a heating rate of 10°C per minute are executed with a cooling cycle at 20°C per minute in between. For the determination of the T_g , the second DSC cycle was analysed with the half height analysis algorithm.

3 RESULTS

The following chapter describes the results concerning solubility and the effects on thermo-mechanical properties of different binder materials.

3.1 BINDER SOLUBILITY

A variety of micrographs for every resin / binder combination has been analysed at different curing temperatures. Only a selection of the most distinct and representative micrographs are presented in this paper.

The HEXION EPIKOTE 05311 does not dissolve at room temperature (RT). A high quantity of binder particles can be detected in the micrographs. With increasing temperature, the amount of particles is significantly reduced and particle edges rounded. At elevated temperatures at 120°C nearly no residue is apparent. Best solubility can be seen in the Resoltech resin. At 60°C only few particles are left and vanish at 120°C.

The E5390 shows similar behaviour as the E5311. At RT binder particles can be detected. When the curing temperature is increased, the remaining particles decrease and at 120°C the binder is completely dissolved in the epoxy resins.

The Araldite LT3366 does not dissolve at room temperature, as it can be seen in Figure 3. Single particle edges can be seen in all epoxy resins. At elevated temperatures (60°C) first changes in appearance are obvious. Less particles can be detected and edges are rounded. At 120°C this observation is even more evident, since only few particles remain in the resin. Furthermore, a halo around the particles is visible. It is assumed, that the halo results from dissolved binder and a local concentration gradient. Due to the high melting temperature of LT3366 between 160 - 200°C, it can be assumed, that the degradation and reduction of the binder particles results from chemical solubility as opposed to melting.

The self-adhesive veil SAERfix EP is compatible with epoxy resins and supposed to participate in the chemical cross-linking during the curing process. SAER has only been analysed in the Resoltech resin and shows, that at RT, only a few remaining binder threads are apparent. At elevated temperatures, these binder fragments completely dissolve in the resin, so that no residue is detectable.

The HEXION MGS PR685 is a hot melt binder, consisting of a high viscous resin component only and is supposed participate in the chemical cross-linking. Micrographs at RT (Figure 3) and elevated temperatures (ET) reveal that the PR685 shows good solubility in all epoxy resins. The fact that even at RT no binder residue is apparent confirms that the PR685 participates in the chemical cross-linking.

Figure 3: Reactive Binder Solubility Analysis; (a) LT3366 (b) PR685

Figure 4: Non-Reactive Binder Solubility Analysis; (a) AIR2E (b) PA1541

The non-reactive, thermoplastic binder veil Spunfab PA1541 is not expected to dissolve in the neat epoxy resin samples. When looking at the micrographs (Figure 4) the assumption is verified. At room

temperature and elevated temperatures no dissolving can be observed. Especially at RT and 60°C a clear outline of the veil structure is evident. The micrograph at 120°C shows a slight difference in appearance. The single thermoplastic threads appear wider and not as sharp as in the other graphs. This can be lead back to the melting temperature of PA1541, which lies between 87-100°C. This change in appearance can therefore be explained by melting of the veil and not by dissolving in the resin.

Similar to PA1541, the spray adhesive AIRTAC 2E is expected not to dissolve in the single neat resin samples due to its rubber-based composition. The solved rubber in the aerosol is foreseen to remain as foreign matter in the resin or subsequent composite materials. As it can be seen in the micrographs (Figure 4) at RT and ET, the AIR2E does not dissolve or change its appearance in none of the three epoxy resins.

For the assessment of binder solubility, a distinction in four different degrees of solubility is selected. Solubility at room temperature implies, that no or only few particles or binder residues are visible in the micrographs. Solubility at elevated temperatures states that after heat application / curing binder particles disappear or the amount of particles is significantly reduced. Binder materials can be classified as partial soluble at ET, when particle edges are clearly rounded and the remaining amount of particles in the micrograph is reduced. No solubility states, that even at elevated temperatures no difference in the binder appearance can be detected and that many binder particles / residue are still detectable in the sample.

Table 2: Solubility Assessment

Binder	CR120	RIM135	Resoltech 1500
E5311	+	+	+
E5390	-	+	++
LT3366	+	-	+
SAER	N.A.	N.A.	+
PR685	++	++	++
PA1541	--	--	--
AIR2E	--	--	--

++ Soluble at RT + Soluble at ET - Partially Soluble at ET -- Not Soluble

3.2 EFFECTS ON THERMO-MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

It is to be expected, that the single binder materials and their solubility behaviour have an impact on the thermo-mechanical properties and the glass transition temperature of the epoxy resins. As stated in the methodology section, only one resin (Resoltech 1500/1504) was analysed in this paper.

As per the technical datasheet of the Resoltech 1500/1504 resin, the glass transition temperature (T_g) is supposed to be 140°C. A benchmark measurement series of six reference samples have been analysed via DSC. An average T_g of 140.84°C with a standard deviation of 0.60 °C confirms the measurement equipment and the testing approach. The subsequent measurements exhibit only small standard deviations of ~ 1°C. The single binder / resin samples are measured against the Resoltech neat resin sample to make a statement about the effects of different tackifying agents on the glass transition temperature. The majority of the reactive and non-reactive binder materials reveal no significant impact on the thermo-mechanical properties of the epoxy resin. As it can be seen in Table 3, E5390, LT3366, SAER, PR685 and PA1541 have a minor effect on the T_g with a ΔT_g of $\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. Special emphasis was set on equal specimen preparation and DSC measurements. However, manual preparation can lead to small deviations in resin mixture. The samples have not been prepared on the same day, so that changes in humidity and room temperature might cause deviations as well. A ΔT_g of 2°C can therefore be accounted for measurement inaccuracy and be neglected.

E5311, however, reveals a T_g reduction of 4°C , comparing to the neat resin sample. The solubility assessment of E5311 shows that at elevated temperatures of 60°C the binder was nearly dissolved in the Resoltech resin and at 120°C no remaining binder particles can be detected (Figure 5). This states that the soluble and reactive tackifying agent E5311 has an effect on the thermo-mechanical properties of the Resoltech resin.

Figure 5: Reactive Binder Solubility Analysis - E5311

The rubber-based spray adhesive AIRTAC 2E reveals a ΔT_g of -9.41°C resulting in a T_g of 131.42°C ($T_{\text{Onset}} = 124.23^\circ\text{C}$), as it can be seen in Table 3 and Figure 6. At all temperature levels binder residue are apparent in the micrographs (Figure 4), stating that AIR2E is not soluble and the effect on the thermo-mechanical properties is evident.

Table 3: DSC Analysis - Measurement Data

	T _g			T _{Onset}		
	AVG	SD	ΔT_g	AVG	SD	ΔT_{Onset}
	[°C]	[°C]	[°C]	[°C]	[°C]	[°C]
Neat Resin	140.84	0.60	--	134.85	1.13	--
E5311	136.81	1.18	-4.03	130.02	2.27	-4.83
E5390	139.22	0.60	-1.62	133.59	0.69	-1.26
LT3366	139.11	0.61	1.73	132.68	1.39	-2.17
SAER	140.52	1.25	-0.32	134.23	2.22	-0.62
PR685	141.46	0.70	0.63	136.13	0.97	1.27
PA1541	142.21	0.99	1.37	136.90	1.10	2.04
AIR2E	131.42	0.43	-9.41	124.23	0.71	-10.63

Figure 6: DSC Analysis

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the Advanced Ply Placement (APP) was introduced as novel technology for automated preforming processes and tape layup. Wrinkle-free placement of wide unidirectional fabrics onto complex double-curved surfaces and molds can be realized, due to segmented gripper units and a shape-adaptive compaction roller. The technology allows automated placement of prepreg materials as well as dry fiber deposition. The lack of fabric adhesion during dry fiber deposition calls for the

utilization of auxiliary binder materials.

Seven different tackifying agents have been analyzed in this study. These binder materials have been applied into three different epoxy resins and cured at varying temperatures. The solubility was subsequently analyzed via micrographs. It has been shown, that the reactive binder systems dissolve in all epoxy resins at elevated temperatures. Only PR685 is already soluble at room temperature and therefore shows superior solubility. Furthermore, it can be stated, that the two non-reactive binder systems PA1541 and AIR2E did not dissolve in the epoxy resins, neither at room temperature nor at elevated temperatures. Binder fragments remained visible and consistent at all times. Therefore, special attention needs to be paid, when applying non-reactive binder materials during preforming or composite manufacturing processes. The tackifying agents will remain as foreign matter in the part and may affect the mechanical, thermo-mechanical and hydro-mechanical properties of the composite part.

To assess the effects on thermo-mechanical properties on neat resin samples additional DSC measurements have been performed. The DSC analysis was used to quantify the change of the glass transition temperature (T_g). The results reveal, that the majority of binder materials have no significant impact on the T_g . A tendency towards reduced glass transition temperatures can be noted. However, a deviation of $\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ can be neglected. E5311 shows a ΔT_g of -4.03°C resulting in a T_g of 136.81°C . A significant change in the T_g can be observed when AIR2E is applied. A ΔT_g of -9.41°C ($T_g = 131.42^\circ\text{C}$) and a Onset Point of $T_{\text{Onset}} = 124.23^\circ\text{C}$ reveals a significant effect on the thermo-mechanical properties of the Resoltech resin. It is to be expected, that the poor solubility of the rubber particles is reason for the T_g reduction and that other epoxy resins will behave similar. However, this statement needs to be verified and quantified in additional DSC measurements. Furthermore, additional studies need to be performed to verify and quantify the effects of different reactive and non-reactive binder systems on the mechanical as well as the hydro-mechanical performance of composite structures. It is to be expected, that the effect of non-reactive binders is more distinct.

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